

Blended Intensive Programme (BIP) experience: co-creating a sustainable learning ecosystem based on an electronic portfolio and AI

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Abstract

This study proposes a pedagogical model aimed to support shared learning among international students during their mobility training programme in Europe. It addresses how Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) can contribute to technical higher education, lifelong learning, and competency development in line with the United Nations Agenda 2030. Specifically, this didactic innovation introduces a collaborative learning ecosystem based on co-creation of knowledge through electronic portfolios and AI. This method was applied within the Blended Intensive Programme (BIP) of the ENHANCE+ European project, focused on the five dimensions of sustainability: People, Planet, Prosperity, Partnerships, and Peace and their relevance for international students from five technical universities across four countries. While further empirical validation is needed, the study provides a design for the integration of significant and active learning, sustainability-oriented content, and digital tools. It also highlights the importance of aligning pedagogical frameworks, learning activities, and e-portfolio-based assessment within international and multilingual mobility.

Keywords: *electronic portfolios, Artificial Intelligence (AI), International mobility, Blended Intensive Programme (BIP), Collaborative learning, Sustainable learning ecosystem, ENHANCEPLUS project, ENHANCE Alliance, Education for Sustainable Development (ESD).*

Resumen

El presente estudio propone un modelo pedagógico destinado a fomentar el aprendizaje compartido entre estudiantes internacionales durante su programa de movilidad en Europa. Aborda cómo la Educación para el Desarrollo Sostenible (EDS) puede contribuir a la educación superior técnica, al aprendizaje permanente y al desarrollo de competencias, en

sintonía con la Agenda 2030 de las Naciones Unidas. En concreto, esta innovación didáctica introduce un ecosistema de aprendizaje colaborativo basado en la cocreación de conocimiento a través de la elaboración de portafolios electrónicos y la inteligencia artificial. Este método se aplicó en el Programa Intensivo Combinado (BIP) del proyecto europeo ENHANCE+, centrado en las cinco dimensiones de la sostenibilidad: Personas, Planeta, Prosperidad, Alianzas y Paz, y su relevancia para estudiantes internacionales de cinco universidades técnicas de cuatro países. Aunque se necesita una mayor validación empírica, el estudio ofrece un diseño para la integración del aprendizaje significativo y activo, los contenidos orientados a la sostenibilidad y el uso de las herramientas digitales. También destaca la importancia de armonizar los marcos pedagógicos, las actividades de aprendizaje y la evaluación basada en el portafolio electrónico en el contexto de la movilidad internacional y multilingüe.

Palabras clave: portafolios electrónicos, Inteligencia Artificial (IA), movilidad internacional, Programa Intensivo Combinado (BIP), aprendizaje colaborativo, ecosistema de aprendizaje sostenible, proyecto ENHANCEPLUS, Alianza ENHANCE, Educación para el Desarrollo Sostenible (EDS).

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